

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF HEALTH-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES IN STUDENTS

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Abstract

The article discusses the methodological level of professional knowledge, which is considered an important pedagogical factor in the development of health care technologies for students, as well as a system of theoretical ideas and skills related to student health, general knowledge. stated about.

Keywords

microelements and vitamins, student health, educational process , health , pedagogical developments , healthy lifestyle , values , intellectual play, medical, hygienic and environmental knowledge, interest in physical education and sports.

The problem of the health of students in the Aral Sea regions lies in the need for teachers to provide medical care and its high level to students, their intellectual and physical potential, ability to work and the formation of a healthy lifestyle. the ability to understand the dependence of the formation of social motives. In particular, providing students with recommended biological microelements and vitamins helps solve the following problems:

- replenish the deficiency of essential nutrients;
- the needs of a particular person, age, gender, characteristics of the work performed, physiological state (pregnancy, lactation (breastfeeding), provision of individual nutrition, taking into account the environmental conditions of the environment);
- provide individual nutrition in case of illness;
- targeted changes in metabolism, increasing the body's tolerance to the effects of adverse environmental factors;
- removal of foreign and toxic substances from the human body;
- change the metabolism of certain substances.

The systematic approach method allows us to consider the student health care system as a set of special activities.

The educational process aimed at healthcare, in determining pedagogical conditions, can act as a model of social existence, since it expresses the paradigm of the ideal level of education and reflects the idea of humanity. Humanistic values of education are social factors worthy of constant attention in modern schools. The universal significance of education, the deeper it involves a person in the world of knowledge, in the process of self-realization and activity, the greater significance it acquires.

According to the results of the experiment, only 17.2% of teachers of the Nukus branch of the Samarkand Institute of Veterinary Medicine gave positive answers to the questionnaire and stated that they knew what measures to take to protect the health of their teachers, they emphasized. ; 22.8% of teachers said that they are not interested in this problem, and 60.0% of respondents believe that this is not necessary, that is, they do not realize the importance of this issue. The results of this survey show that the continuous development of professional skills of school teachers is not only a pedagogical, but also an important social problem.

Our research shows that continuous improvement of professional and pedagogical qualifications as an important pedagogical factor in the development of health care technologies implies:

- 1) increase the methodological level of professional knowledge in the field of healthcare;
- 2) mastering practical skills and theoretical knowledge aimed at introducing technologies aimed at protecting the health of students;
- 3) students acquire skills and master technical means associated with the use of basic tools for researching life support systems;
- 4) integration of students' health skills and theoretical concepts with general knowledge.

Reforming educational processes aimed at protecting health is directly related to the denial of the regressive, dominant position of the teacher, changing the criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the educational process. The role and work style of a teacher are fundamentally different from the subject-oriented educational process, which is based on an information-control function and an authoritarian-directive management style that limits the student's initiative. The task of organizing and motivating the teacher takes a leading place, as a result of which the subject of student health protection is considered as an integral person who comes into contact with all participants in the educational process.

The motivational and intellectual attitudes of the teacher are freed from the limitations of their own thinking and experience, based on the ideas of cooperation,

joint activities, health care, aimed at a healthy lifestyle for students. To organize the educational process based on humanitarian ideas, the teacher must have high professional skills. A high level of professional skill of the teaching staff of educational institutions is ensured on the basis of:

- 1) the real readiness of a teacher of an educational institution, acting on the basis of educational content aimed at health, for the educational process;
- 2) compliance of the level of pedagogical skills achieved by teachers with the objectives of the educational program aimed at healthcare;
- 3) a sufficient level of knowledge of students in the field of healthcare, as provided for by state educational standards.

In our opinion, the continuous professional development of teachers is their main resource for the wise use of temporary resources based on independent work and advice from highly qualified specialists. Accordingly, in our research work we developed criteria for determining the professional and pedagogical skills of teachers of general education institutions at the stage of transition to the educational process focused on health care. These criteria can be conditionally grouped according to the criteria of professional pedagogical excellence and socio-professional prestige.

Professional pedagogical skills, in turn, include professional pedagogical training and professional pedagogical activities.

Social and professional prestige is determined by the social prestige of the teacher, in particular, his place in the education system and the correspondence of the level of professional skill to socially significant goals.

In order for a teacher to fully and effectively fulfill his duties, it is necessary to have a wide range of skills, including technical knowledge and skills, develop organizational skills, and use the situation wisely. Ultimately, only the teacher determines and directs the innovative and health-improving essence of the educational process.

The teacher is not only a carrier of information and data, but also the main assistant in the formation and development of the student's personality. The first component changes the content of students' educational activities, as well as their personal approaches from learning and assessment to active communication with the teacher and other classmates who are considered participants in the educational process.

The second important component is associated with changes in the structure and function of knowledge, which are achieved on the basis of innovative education, that is, through methods of organizing the assimilation process. If

knowledge is based on modern information, it allows a person to take a certain place at the stage of cultural development as a “third social force” after material and spiritual wealth and personal influence. In this case, the acquisition of knowledge does not take the form of reproductive, dry memorization, but as a productive creative process; various forms of organizing intellectual activity of a research nature are developed.

We have created specific developments for the design and practical application of health-oriented educational technologies in unfavorable environmental regions. For example, we recommend the following development for health education technologies.

The purpose of the training: to form in children and adolescents a value-based approach to their health.

Responsibilities:

- show the relevance of STT and health problems;
 - determine the initial level of students and their attitude to health care;
- Formation of the need for exercises related to physical training.

Student manuals: A-4 sheets of paper, pens, pencils, “Health Attitude Index” tests, sheets with incomplete sentences like “When I’m sick, I don’t want to...”, version of the FSMU-formula. .

All materials are prepared for each student in the class .

Transfer form

- 2-4 courses of training (practice);
- 5-9 courses of study (practice);
- Intellectual game for students of professional colleges of levels 1-3.

Lesson duration 40 minutes.

Below is a sample plan for health lessons with a high school student. Depending on the wishes of the student, additional materials can be added taking into account the specifics of the area or region.

Student's introductory speech . 2010 is a special year for our republic. By decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan it was declared the “Year of the Ideal Generation”. That is why today we will talk about the need to be slim and healthy.

1-2 courses .

Plan:

Part I – Creative task. A poster competition on promoting a healthy lifestyle will be held.

Part II – Intellectual game “Healthy body - healthy soul” (25-30 min.).

Materials needed to organize the first part of the lesson:

- 4 sheets of A2 paper,
- oil pencil,
- glasses,
- flomasters,
- markers,
- pencils (4 sets),
- 4 colored dice (25x25x25), exactly one colored dice for each team.

At the beginning of the lesson, students are divided into 4 groups. Grouping can be done in different ways, for example, by blood type, eye color, zodiac sign and other qualities. Organized teams choose a name for themselves.

He explains to the student that today's lesson is devoted to the most pressing problem - the formation of a healthy lifestyle and introduces the components of a healthy lifestyle:

- 1) *quit smoking;*
- 2) *abstinence from alcohol;*
- 3) *abstinence from drugs;*
- 4) *absence of various diseases;*
- 5) *engage in physical education and sports;*
- 6) *don't say bad words.*

The first part of the lesson - the teams are given the task: within 5-10 minutes, draw a poster promoting a healthy lifestyle.

Requirements for the image on the poster: brightness, imagery, memorability, information content, originality.

Posters will be judged based on these criteria.

The winning team will receive 10 game coins, the rest will receive 5 game coins. These posters will decorate the stage.

The second part of the lesson consists of 4 stages. At each stage, the rules and content of the questions change.

Step 1 is performed individually with each team. The student asks the team to roll the dice and determine how many points they can get for the correct answer. Each team can roll the dice once.

Questions for the first round ("Quit smoking!"):

1. Even at the beginning of the last century, American doctors knew that it was harmful for pregnant women to gain weight. But the tools they recommended are great for us today. American doctors advised women to exercise less, not eat sweets, and what else should they not do to lose weight? (smoking)

2. According to Khalfan Maher, former director of the World Health Organization, which common disease is preventable? (smoking)

3. Bismarck's family doctor told him that smoking was prohibited and testified that the habit was negatively affecting his health. But Bismarck said that his art of diplomacy was just that. What kind of art is this? (people cover their eyes with smoke).

4. It became fashionable after World War II. This was usually done at home or in the office. But in 1957, doctors proved that this habit has a negative effect on the body. People with such a habit are not even hired in the same places? What custom are we talking about? (smoking)

5. According to A.P. Chekhov, "Kissing a smoking woman is equal to..." What? (Cinderella's Kiss)

The 2nd stage is held jointly with all teams. The teacher orders the teams to throw the dice. The team with the most points begins to answer the question. The score for this question is equal to points cubed. Questions of this type are asked on the topic "Drugs, alcohol - no."

1. What did ancient Greek philosophers call a person who had a sore neck? (drug addict, from Greek narke - addiction, mania - get used to).

2. According to A.P. Chekhov, "vodka, even if it is white, turns the nose red,... darkens it." What makes it dark? (reputation)

3. According to the Chinese proverb, what brings a hundred worries and one joy? (Alcoholic drinks)

4. In France, a quarter of young people die from this disease. What kind of disease is this (Alcoholism)

5. What drinks are prohibited in Islam (Alcoholic drinks)

The 3rd stage is held separately for each team.

Questions for the third stage "We are not afraid of any diseases!"

1. According to doctors, the most common infectious disease is influenza. Which disease is considered non-infectious? (caries)

2. What disease, according to the Greeks, breaks the mind and spirit? (schizophrenia)

3. According to the World Health Organization, polio is one of the occupational diseases of school teachers. This disease is not a serious disease and is present in the life of every person. Show symptoms of this disease (gray hair)

4. In the United States, these creatures are the main spreaders of influenza. They are responsible for the autumn epidemic. Who are they? (Pupils)

Stage 4 is held jointly with all teams. The teacher orders to throw the dice. Each team answers the number of questions indicated in the cube. For each correct answer 3 points are given.

Questions for the fourth stage "If you say you will be healthy, do it!"

1. The inventor of this thing said about his invention: "This thing serves to transport and shorten letters." What is this? (bike)

2. According to P. Bragg, doctors 9. Starting from the fourth, these are: natural nutrition, hunger, sports, rest, proper physique and intelligence. Name the first three doctors (Sun, Air, Water)

3. What sport is referred to in the following English phrase: "It is the exchange of knowledge through gestures" (boxing)

4. In ancient Greece, athletics was for a long time the only type of athletics at the Olympic Games. What type was it? (run)

5. This physics game was created by a simple apple. What kind of game is it? (badminton)

6. What was the process of delivering express mail called in the 18th century? (Relay)

Note to teacher:

All teams participate in answering all questions. But they receive different points for correct answers. These points are determined by the points of the cube. The "main player" can have points in the cube, and the other five teams receive 1 point for each correct answer. Therefore, at the end of the game, it is necessary to reward teams that have given many correct answers.

Points are calculated at the end of the lesson. The winner is the team with the most points.

The development of this lesson is aimed at creating a healthy lifestyle as a value, in which, through intellectual games and competitions, students' responsibility for their own health will increase and their view of the environment will change. Environmental knowledge increases, interest in physical education and sports awakens.

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